

About the Drinker Paradox

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We refer the reader to the Wikipedia entry https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Drinker_paradox for the Drinker Paradox. Unless otherwise stated, we use the terminology and notation of the book [1]. An exception to this rule is that we regard the symbols \top (true) and \perp (false) as sentences [1,§27.3] of First-Order Logic. Let the setting of First-Order Logic be in force.

We fix once and for all a variable x . We call **special formula** a formula \mathcal{A} [1,§27.2] such that no variable other than x occurs freely in \mathcal{A} . (The variable x may or may not occur freely in \mathcal{A} .) Assume that, to each special formula \mathcal{A} is attached a special formula $\Phi\mathcal{A}$ and a special formula $\Psi\mathcal{A}$ in such a way that

$$\forall x (\mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{B}) \rightarrow \forall x (\Phi\mathcal{A} \rightarrow \Phi\mathcal{B}), \quad (1)$$

$$\forall x (\mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{B}) \rightarrow \forall x (\Psi\mathcal{A} \leftarrow \Psi\mathcal{B}), \quad (2)$$

$$(\Phi\mathcal{A})(a) \leftrightarrow \Phi(\mathcal{A}(a)) \text{ and } (\Psi\mathcal{A})(a) \leftrightarrow \Psi(\mathcal{A}(a)) \quad (3)$$

for all name a [1,§27.1]. (Can you see the difference between (1) and (2)?) Note that $\forall x (\mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{B})$, $\forall x (\Phi\mathcal{A} \rightarrow \Phi\mathcal{B})$, $\forall x (\mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{B})$ and $\forall x (\Phi\mathcal{A} \rightarrow \Phi\mathcal{B})$ are **sentences** (see footnote 1). We also assume that Φ and Ψ map sentences to sentences.

Theorem. *In the above setting, we have*

$$\exists x \Phi\mathcal{A} \leftrightarrow \Phi\exists x\mathcal{A},$$

$$\forall x \Phi\mathcal{A} \leftrightarrow \Phi\forall x\mathcal{A},$$

$$\exists x \Psi\mathcal{A} \leftrightarrow \Psi\forall x\mathcal{A}, \quad (4)$$

$$\forall x \Psi\mathcal{A} \leftrightarrow \Psi\exists x\mathcal{A}.$$

In particular, the Drinker Paradox follows from (4). Indeed, let \mathcal{A} be a special formula and \mathcal{S} a **sentence**. For convenience we write $\mathcal{A}(x)$ for \mathcal{A} , and we define $(\Psi\mathcal{A})(x)$ as $\mathcal{A}(x) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}$. Then (4) implies

$$\exists x (\mathcal{A}(x) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}) \leftrightarrow (\forall x \mathcal{A}(x) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}).$$

Letting \mathcal{S} be $\forall y \mathcal{A}(y)$ yields

$$\exists x (\mathcal{A}(x) \rightarrow \forall y \mathcal{A}(y)) \leftrightarrow (\forall x \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \forall y \mathcal{A}(y)) \leftrightarrow \top.$$

This implies $\exists x (\mathcal{A}(x) \rightarrow \forall y \mathcal{A}(y))$, which is the Drinker Paradox.

Our proof of the theorem will contain formal and informal parts. We have verified the formal parts with the proof checker [2], and we will give links to the relevant screenshots.

We say that the special formulas \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} are **equivalent** if $\forall x (\mathcal{A} \leftrightarrow \mathcal{B})$ (this is an equivalence relation). In particular, equivalent special formulas are mapped by Φ and Ψ to equivalent special formulas, and equivalent sentences to equivalent sentences. We also say that a sentence is **true** if it is equivalent to \top , and that it is **false** if it is equivalent to \perp .

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Proposition. *A sentence is either true and not false, or false and not true.*

We will give a formal proof of the proposition. More precisely, we will prove a chain of lemmas implying the proposition, and, for each lemma, we will give a proof which has been verified by the proof checker [2]. In the checker [2] the statements are called **arguments**. An argument has a (possibly empty) finite set of assumptions, and a conclusion. The assumptions are separated by commas, and the conclusion is preceded by the symbol \therefore (“therefore”). We will write the following statements in the syntax of arguments and prove them formally.

(a) \top Link: <https://imgur.com/KPG6NGN>

$$\begin{array}{l|l} 1 & \perp \\ 2 & \top \quad \neg\text{I } 1-1 \end{array}$$

(b) $A \vee \neg A$ Link: <https://imgur.com/e9VADSi>

$$\begin{array}{l|l} 1 & A \\ 2 & A \vee \neg A \quad \vee\text{I } 1 \\ 3 & \neg A \\ 4 & A \vee \neg A \quad \vee\text{I } 3 \\ 5 & A \vee \neg A \quad \text{LEM } 1-2, 3-4 \end{array}$$

(c) $A, \neg A \therefore \perp$ Link: <https://imgur.com/kycgB5E>

$$\begin{array}{l|l} 1 & A \\ 2 & \neg A \\ 3 & \perp \quad \neg\text{E } 1,2 \end{array}$$

We claim

$$(d) A \leftrightarrow (A \leftrightarrow \top)$$

In view of (a), this is equivalent to $A \leftrightarrow (\top \rightarrow A)$. We have clearly $A \therefore \top \rightarrow A$, and also $\top \rightarrow A \therefore A$ by (a).

We claim

$$(e) \neg A \leftrightarrow (A \leftrightarrow \perp)$$

Since we always have $\perp \rightarrow A$, (e) is equivalent to $\neg A \leftrightarrow (A \rightarrow \perp)$, and thus to the conjunction of $\neg A, A \therefore \perp$, which is (c), and $A \rightarrow \perp \therefore \neg A$, which follows from the introduction rule for \neg [1,§17.8]. This completes the proof of the proposition.

We prove the theorem.

In view of the proposition we have $\Phi \mathcal{S} \leftrightarrow \mathcal{S}$ for all sentence \mathcal{S} , or there is some \mathcal{S}_0 such that $\Phi \mathcal{S} \leftrightarrow \mathcal{S}_0$ for all sentence \mathcal{S} .

Similarly, we have $\Psi\mathcal{S} \leftrightarrow \neg\mathcal{S}$ for all sentence \mathcal{S} , or there is some sentence \mathcal{S}_0 such that $\Psi\mathcal{S} \leftrightarrow \mathcal{S}_0$ for all sentence \mathcal{S} .

Let \mathcal{A} be a special formula. Then (3) implies that we have $\Phi\mathcal{A} \leftrightarrow \mathcal{A}$ for all special formula \mathcal{A} , or there is some sentence \mathcal{S}_0 such that $\Phi\mathcal{S} \leftrightarrow \mathcal{S}_0$ for all special formula \mathcal{A} ; and that we have $\Psi\mathcal{A} \leftrightarrow \neg\mathcal{A}$ for all special formula \mathcal{A} , or there is some sentence \mathcal{S}_0 such that $\Psi\mathcal{S} \leftrightarrow \mathcal{S}_0$ for all special formula \mathcal{A} .

As a result, we can assume that, for all special formula \mathcal{A} , the formula $\Phi\mathcal{A}$ is \mathcal{A} , or there is some sentence \mathcal{S}_0 such that $\Phi\mathcal{A}$ is \mathcal{S}_0 , and that the formula $\Psi\mathcal{A}$ is $\neg\mathcal{A}$, or there is some sentence \mathcal{S}_0 such that $\Psi\mathcal{A}$ is \mathcal{S}_0 .

To prove the theorem under these assumptions, it suffices to verify the arguments below.

$\exists xA \therefore A$ Link: <https://imgur.com/UKArkNC>

1	$\exists xA$		
2	<table style="border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="border-bottom: 1px solid black; padding-right: 5px;">A</td> </tr> </table>	A	
A			
3	A	$\exists E$ 1, 2-2	

$\forall xA \therefore A$ Link: <https://imgur.com/blDE2zc>

1	$\forall xA$		
2	<table style="border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="border-bottom: 1px solid black; padding-right: 5px;">A</td> </tr> </table>	A	$\forall E$ 1
A			

References

- [1] Magnus, P. D., et al. *forall x: Calgary. An Introduction to Formal Logic*. (2023). <https://forallx.openlogicproject.org/>.
- [2] Proof checker <https://proofs.openlogicproject.org/>.